

Spectrophotometric determination of mercury in water samples using 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone acetoxyhydrazone

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Manuscript received 23 April 2013, revised 22 July 2013, accepted 12 September 2013

Abstract : A very simple, highly selective, direct and non-extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of trace amounts of mercury(II) is developed using newly synthesized 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone acetoxyhydrazone (DAAH). The reagent reacts with mercury(II) in a slightly acidic medium (pH 6.5, sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer) to form yellow coloured 1 : 1 (M : L) complex. The colour reaction is instantaneous and absorbance values remain constant for 3 h. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of DAAH method are found to be $2.5 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.080 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of mercury(II) respectively. The linear calibration graphs were obtained for 1.0–9.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of mercury(II). The detection limit and relative standard deviation are found to be 0.0782 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 2.60% respectively. The method is successfully applied to a number of water samples (potable and polluted) containing mercury(II). The results of the proposed method in the analysis of water samples are comparable with those obtained by dithizone method and were found to be in good agreement.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, mercury determination, 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone acetoxyhydrazone, water samples.

Introduction

Drinking water is the one of the basic needs of life and essential for survival. In India, ground water is being used as raw water for 85% public water supply. In 1970's of the approximately 2.5 billion people in developing world, only 38% has safer drinking water. At the beginning of 1980's water supply coverage was 75% in urban areas and 46% in rural areas. In developing countries 75% of the population had access to water supply. So, they are always prone to loss of their lives (or) cost a big toll to save themselves from the occurrence of different water-borne diseases.

Among metal pollutants mercury is one of the most hazardous toxic metal in the marine environment. Mercury has high toxic nature both in its organics and inorganic forms¹. But organo-mercuric compounds are more toxic in which methyl mercury compounds are considered as the "VILLAINS" in all fatal incidents due to mercury. Water is contaminating by the presence of heavy metals, metal pollutants, pesticides, chemicals and pathogenic agents which is hazardous to human health. The permissible limits of some cations and anions in drinking

water supply by many medical research institutions are given in Table 1.

All these findings cause great concern regarding public health demanding an accurate determination of mercury in different water samples. The analytical monitoring of mercury in water samples become a challenge for an analytical chemist. Several authors have reported on the extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of mercury(II) in which it forms insoluble complexes with reagents in the aqueous phase which necessarily be extracted with various solvents and most of them are non recoverable and expensive too.

Hydrazones are interesting analytical reagents as these are capable of forming chelates (or) inner complex salts in addition of containing acidic groupings² and coordinating groups containing nitrogen and oxygen. In the light of the above and in continuation of our previous work³⁻⁶ on the analytical applications of hydrazones, we report here the spectrophotometric determination of mercury in different water samples using 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone acetoxyhydrazone (DAAH). A close literature survey reveals that DAAH (Fig. 1) is so far not been

Table 1. Permissible limits of drinking water quality

Parameters	USEPA	WHO	ISI	ICMR	CPCB
pH	6.5–8.5	6.5–8.5	6.5–8.5	6.5–9.2	6.5–8.5
Conductivity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	–	–	–	–	2000
Alkalinity (mg/L)	600	–	–	–	–
Total hardness (mg/L)	–	500	300	600	600
Mercury (mg/L)	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	–
Lead (mg/L)	–	0.05	0.05	0.05	No
relaxation					
Iron (mg/L)	–	0.1	0.3	1.0	1.0
Calcium (mg/L)	–	75	75	200	200
Magnesium (mg/L)	–	50	30	–	100
Copper (mg/L)	1.3	1.0	0.05	1.5	1.5
Cadmium (mg/L)	0.005	0.01	–	–	No
Arsenic (mg/L)	0.05	0.01	–	–	–
Zinc (mg/L)	–	5.0	5.0	0.10	15.0
Chromium (mg/L)	0.1	–	0.05	–	No
Chlorides (mg/L)	250	200	250	1000	1000
Nitrates (mg/L)	–	–	45	100	100
Sulphates (mg/L)	–	–	150	400	400

USEPA – US Environmental Protection Agency, USA.

WHO – World Health Organization, Geneva.

ISI – Indian Statistical Institute, Benguluru, India.

ICMR – Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi, India.

CPCB – Central Pollution Control Board, Delhi, India.

Fig. 1. Structure of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone acetylhydrazone (SAAH).

employed for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).

Results and discussion

The reagent DAAH easily prepared (Fig. 2) under reflux conditions. The reagent has been characterized using IR, NMR and Mass spectral data. The infrared spectrum of DAAH (Fig. 3) showed bands (cm^{-1}) at 3461(s), 3235(s), 1662(s), 1627(s), 1581(s), 1451(m), 1296(s), 751(s) and 696(m) are respectively assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretching, $\nu(\text{NH})$ secondary stretch, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ amide stretch, $\nu(\text{NH})$ in plane bending, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ azomethine

Fig. 2. The synthesis of DAAH.

stretch, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ asymmetric bending, $\nu(\text{CO})$ stretch, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ aromatic *oop* bend and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ aromatic *oop* bend respectively. ^1H NMR spectrum of DAAH ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) (Fig. 4) showed signals (δ ppm) at 2.02, 2.26, 6.25, 7.36, 9.80 and 10.76 due to $-\text{CH}_3$ protons (azomethine), $-\text{COCH}_3$ protons, phenyl protons, imine protons, *p*-phenolic protons and *o*-phenolic protons of DAAH respectively. Mass spectrum of DAAH shows molecular ion signal at m/z 208 corresponding to its molecular formula.

Absorption spectra of 2×10^{-5} M solutions of DAAH at different pH values were recorded and pK_a values were determined spectrophotometrically using Phillip and Merritt method⁷. The values of deprotonation of DAAH are 3.8 (pK_1) and 7.5 (pK_2) corresponding to the formation of enol form and conjugated mono anion form respectively (Scheme 1). The chromogenic characteristics of DAAH are given in Table 2.

Scheme 1. A general scheme showing enolization and deprotonation of keto group.

A 0.01 M solution of reagent is stable for 3 h. The colour reaction of reagent with mercury(II) is instantaneous at room temperature. The order of addition of metal ion, reagent and buffer has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. Various physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of the mercury complex are summarized in Table 3. Stoichiometry of the complex ($\text{M} : \text{L} = 1 : 1$) is determined by Job's continuous variation method and

Fig. 3. IR spectrum of DAAH in KBr disc.

Fig. 4. ¹H NMR spectrum of DAAH in DMSO-*d*₆ medium.

Table 2. The chromogenic characteristics of DAAH

Metal ion	λ_{\max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity ^a	pH range	Colour of the complex
Hg ^{II}	374	2.5×10^4	6.5–7.5	Yellow
Cu ^{II}	370	1.0×10^4	4.0–6.5	Yellow
Pb ^{II}	380	1.2×10^4	5.0–7.0	Pale yellow
Co ^{II}	365	2.0×10^4	6.0–7.5	Deep yellow
Ni ^{II}	375	1.8×10^4	5.5–7.0	Pale greenish yellow

^aL mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

molar ratio method. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 6.5), equimolar solutions of mercury(II) and reagent were used in these studies. The dissociation constant (α) and concentration (c) of the reagent at intersecting point are used in the calculation of stability constant of the complex. Stability constant of 1 : 1 (M : L) complex is calculated using the following equation,

$$\beta = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2c \quad (1)$$

Based on the composition and survey of literature⁸, the structure of the complex (Fig. 5) is predicted.

Table 3. The physico-chemical and analytical properties of Hg^{II} complex of DAAH

Sl. No.	Characteristics	Hg-DAAH
1.	λ_{\max} (nm)	374
2.	Mean absorbance	0.234 ± 0.0002
3.	pH range (optimum)	5.5–7.0
4.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full colour development	10 fold
5.	Time stability of the complex (h)	3
6.	Beer's law validity rang ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.0–9.0
7.	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	2.5×10^4
8.	Specific absorptivity (ml g ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.124
9.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2$)	0.080
10.	Composition of the complex as obtained in Job's and molar ratio methods (M : L)	1 : 1
11.	Stability constant of the complex	8.7×10^4
12.	Standard deviation in the determination of 3.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Hg ^{II} for ten determinations	0.0061
13.	Relative standard deviation	2.60
14.	Detection limit ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) ^a	0.0782
15.	Determination limit ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) ^b	0.23

^aDetection limit = Standard deviation \times 3/Mean ($\mu\text{g/mL}$).

^bDetermination limit S/N = 10.

Tolerance limits of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions which often accompany mercury has been studied by

Fig. 5. Structure of Hg-DAAH complex.

adding different amounts of foreign ions to fixed amount of mercury(II) solution. The colour reactions are studied as described in the standard/recommended procedure. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance of the reaction mixture was considered tolerable. Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} do not interfere in the presence of masking agents viz. thiocyanate and citrate respectively. The tolerance limit values of foreign ions are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of foreign ions in the determination of (3.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of mercury

Ion added	Tolerance limit	Ion added	Tolerance limit
Tartrate	592	Mo ^{VI}	39
Citrate	544	Mn ^{II}	22
Sulphate	384	Zn ^{IIa}	18
Oxalate	176	Ag ^I	17
Chloride	141	Co ^{II}	11
Fluoride	76	Ni ^{II}	3
Iodide	50	Cu ^{IIb}	2
Phosphate	38	Fe ^{III}	1
Bromide	9	Al ^{III}	0.5
Nitrate	2		
EDTA	1		
Hypo	0.3		
Thiourea	0.1		

^aIn the presence of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of thiocyanate.

^bIn the presence of 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of citrate.

Applications : The present method was successfully applied for the determination of mercury when present alone. The developed method was also applied to the determination of mercury(II) in various water samples (Table 5). The results obtained are comparable to the data obtained using dithizone method⁹. The present method

is simple, rapid and sensitive for non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in aqueous medium.

Table 5. Determination of mercury in water samples

Sample	Amount of mercury ^a found (µg/mL)	
	DAAH method	Dithizone method
Tap water ^b	0.011	0.010
Pond water ^c	0.565	0.562
Tank water ^d	0.015	0.016
Drain water ^e	2.080	2.076
River water ^f	1.050	1.030

^aAverage of five determinations. ^bAkuthotapalli tap water. ^cMadanapalle pond water. ^dMadanapalle tank water. ^eMadanapalle drain water. ^fPennahobilam river water.

Experimental

Preparation of DAAH : The reaction mixture containing 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (resacetophenone) (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) in 10 mL ethanol and acetichydrazide (0.74 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in 5 mL of ethanol were taken in 250 mL round bottom flask and refluxed with stirring for 3 h. A pale brown coloured product was separated out on cooling the reaction mixture. It was collected by filtration and washed several times with hot water and 50% cold methanol. This compound was recrystallised from methanol and dried in vacuum. Percentage of yield is 82 : m.p. 243–245 °C. The condensation reaction is given in Fig. 3. The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 52 mg of the compound in dimethylformamide (DMF) in 25-mL volumetric flask. The reagent solution was stable for 10 h.

1 M Hydrochloric acid – 1 M sodium acetate (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M sodium acetate – 0.2 M acetic acid (pH 4.0–6.5) and 0.2 M ammonium chloride – 0.2 M ammonium solution (pH 7.5–10.5) were used in the present study.

A 1×10^{-2} M stock solution of divalent mercury was prepared by dissolving 0.272 g of mercuric chloride (Merck, Darmstadt) in deionized water containing few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and made up to the mark in a 100-mL volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were standardised¹⁰ with EDTA using xylenol orange as an indicator. Solutions of large number of inorganic ions, complexing agents were prepared from their AnalaR grade or equivalent grade water soluble salts.

Recommended procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing mercury in optimum concentration range (Table 3), 10 mL of buffer solution (pH 6.5) and 1 mL 0.01 M reagent were combined in 25-mL volumetric standard flasks and resulted solution was diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 374 nm against reagent (DAAH) blank. The measured absorbance was used to compute the amount of mercury from predetermined calibrated plot.

Water sample collection and preservation : Water samples were collected in polyethylene bottles from tap wells, river, sea and drain of different places. After collection, 2 mL of concentrated nitric acid was added as preservative. Each filtered (with Whatman No. 40) environmental water sample (250 mL) was mixed with concentrated nitric acid in a 500 mL distillation flask. The sample was digested in the presence of an excess KMnO₄ solution according to the method recommended by Fifield *et al.*¹¹. The solution was cooled and neutralized with diluted ammonium hydroxide solution. The digest was transferred into a 25-mL calibrated flask and diluted up to the mark with deionised water.

Instrumentation : Perkin-Elmer (Lambda 25) UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm (path length) quartz cell and Elico model LI-610 pH meter were used in the present study.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank M. Subbalakshmi of IICT, Hyderabad for her help in recording IR and NMR spectra of reagent sample.

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